

MEDICAL RADIOLOGY IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS CRITICISM OF PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION IN SCIENCE TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING OPERATIVE THINKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822781>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10- Sentabr 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15- Sentabr 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 21- Sentabr 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

Medical images, analog form, digital forms, pixels, matrix their main advantages when switching to a system in the form of images accuracy and high quality.

ABSTRACT

In medicine, the role of medical images in the field of radiology is very important great importance. Medical to the attending physician in making a precise diagnosis for the patient. The clarity of the images and the high quality of the images are very good importance. Processing, storage, transformation of medical images conversion from analog to digital form..

In medicine, doctors mainly use medical imaging to diagnose and treat patients. Medical imaging is a combination of clinical analysis and medical imaging. creating visual images of the internal structures of the body for intervention, as well as some. The method and process of visual representation of the functions of organs or tissues allows the non-medical imager to examine the internal structures hidden by the skin and bones, as well as to diagnose diseases.

The medical imaging industry has a number of technological devices that provide doctors with various images in their diagnostic processes. They are also called diagnostic images.

Methods of obtaining medical images consist of radiation diagnostic methods, X-ray, magnetic resonance, radionuclide and ultrasound. Medical images can be divided into two groups: digital and analog. Analog images are continuous data are the images it contains. Like all analog images, medical images have their drawbacks. Medical images in analog form are more blurred and sharper than digital images. Doctors want more medical images accuracy and clarity. This is due to the fact that doctors have a high level of error in diagnosis. Continuous to analog images includes images containing character information. These images are presented to the doctor to diagnose diseases.

All analog images, including medical images, have flaws. In particular, it is difficult to store them, process them according to diagnostics, and transfer them from computer to computer. In analog form, the quality of the images is accompanied by a lot of unnecessary signals. There are also annoying noises.

Various medical images, regardless of how they are imaged, can be combined into two main groups: analog and digital. Images first, they are created in analog quality, and then they

are digitized during the transmission from the detector to the display. Analog images: traditional cinema radiography, including linear tomography; conventional fluoroscopy sonography (Ultra sound waves are emitted from structures in the body and diagnostic medical examination for imaging). This check is often simply called ultrasound or sonography. Analog-digital images: digital radiography (secondary digitization of radiography), digital fluoroscopy, digital subtraction angiography, • sonography, scintigraphy (internal radio for creating two-dimensional images use of nuclides) Digital imaging: the primary of radiography digital methods; computed tomography, magnetic resonance tomography, emission tomography (one- and two-photon), Doppler mapping. There are two types of diagnostic images on the monitor possible The latter has a graphic nature and is selected by a doctor according to the programs can be changed without spoiling the image quality.

In this article, the role of medical images in medicine is very important, In addition, it is an auxiliary instruction for doctors in making accurate diagnoses for patients that we can see in fate. Also worldwide disability or death of patients due to doctors' mistakes we can see that. Accuracy of images in diagnosis and

The high quality of the images prevents the attending physician from making mistakes will be taken. In solving this problem, there is a priority, all medical devices In modern conditions, the prevalence of all medical specialists is high that they have qualifications, that there are no errors in diagnosing patients we are sure. The location of the injury is clearly defined by the clarity of the image we can see, for example, a tumor located in the patient's brain, a computer tomography shows its size, diameter, depth of location that we can express in centimeters, to a patient with a broken leg and shoulder in traumatology the quality, accuracy and clarity of the images in making an accurate diagnosis to the doctor not to make mistakes, and this is the right decision in choosing the right method for treating the disease we consider.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that whatever is related to medicine If our images are clear, crisp and high quality, our doctors diagnose patients they do not face difficulties in putting.

References:

1. Медицинский изображения и их обработка. <http://masters.donntu.edu.ua/2012/fknt/panina/article3.htm>
2. Радиолгическая информационная система. <http://www.kmis.ru/site.nsf/pages/ris.htm>
3. . Архивирование данных в медицинских учреждениях. <http://emag.iis.ru>
4. . THE METHOD OF USING THE FUNCTIONAL-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION IN DETECTING PARASITES IN CHILDREN. R Bakhramov, M Malikov, A Kubaev -Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation;32(3) 2021. P 136-140 <https://turkjphysiotherrehabil.org> ТИББИЙ ТАСВИРЛАРНИ ТИББИЁТДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ.
5. 5. LABORATORY INFORMATION SYSTEMS. SS Nabiyeva, OB Axmedov, MR Malikov, LE Shukurov -Archive of Conferences, 2020. <https://scholar.google.com>
6. 6. WhatisEcology? /KhudaykulovaSH.N., KubaevA.E., JalilovM.X., Baratova R.SH., Kurbanova L.M., Umarova O.S., Burxonov B.N. Annalsof R.S.C.B., ISSN:1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue5, Pages. 3341-3345 2021; <http://annalsofrscb.ro6>.
7. 7. Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 12 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1385 Scientific Journal Impact Factor (SJIF) 2021: 5.723 Directory Indexing of International

Research Journals-CiteFactor 2020-21: 0.89 DOI: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021- 12-5-87.Academic Research, Uzbekistan www.ares.uz

8. FORMATION OF STUDENTS ' SKILLS IN USING THE INTERNET AND HIT THE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.Kubaev A.E, Abdullaeva S. B 10.Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(2), 748-75111.<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/137412>.

9. Ахборот хавфсизлиги: асосий тушунчалар.Таҳдидлар ва уларнинг турлари. Ахборот хавфсизлиги сиёсати мавзусидаги маруза дарсни модул тизимида онлай нутиш.

10. KubayevA.E, Ne'matovN.I.14.Хоразм Маъmun академияси ахборотномаси: илмий журнал.-No1 (85)2022-2, Стр. -290-300.<http://mamun.uz/uz/page/56>.

11. Шукурова, С. (2023). МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО ОПЕРАТИВНОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ ЧЕРЕЗ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ДИАЛОГ ПРИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ РАДИОЛОГИИ В ВЫСШИХ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ. Наука и инновация, 1(20), 89-91. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/si/article/view/19985>

12. Шукурова, С. . (2023). ТИББИЁТ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАСАССАЛАРИДА ТИББИЙ РАДИОЛОГИЯ ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК МУЛОҚОТ ВОСИТАСИДА ТАНҚИДИЙ ОПЕРАТИВ ТАФАККУРНИ ЎСТИРИШ МЕТОДИКАСИ. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 2(23), 104-106. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/zdit/article/view/19987>

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